

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES RELATED TO THE CERVICAL CANCER AMONG BSN STUDENTS:

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Abstract

Background:

Cervical cancer is a major public health concern, especially in developing countries like Pakistan. It is mainly caused by persistent infection with human papillomavirus (HPV) and is preventable through vaccination and early screening. However, lack of awareness and poor preventive practices contribute to its high burden.

Objectives:

This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to cervical cancer among BSN students and to identify gaps in awareness and preventive behaviors.

Methods:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at Liaquat College of Nursing, Jamshoro. A total of 80 BSN students were selected using simple random sampling. Data were collected through a structured, self-administered questionnaire. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used for data analysis.

Results:

The findings showed that most students had moderate knowledge about cervical cancer and its symptoms. Positive attitudes toward prevention were observed, with many students willing to seek medical help. However, preventive practices were inadequate, with low screening participation and limited awareness of HPV vaccination. Fear, embarrassment, and misconceptions were identified as barriers to screening.

Conclusion:

Although students have basic knowledge and positive attitudes, there is a gap between knowledge and practice. Educational programs and awareness campaigns are needed to improve cervical cancer prevention. Infrastructure limit access to preventive services. Studies show that many women and even healthcare students have insufficient knowledge about cervical cancer and its prevention (Jafri et al., 2018). This highlights the need for further research in this area.

INTRODUCTION

Cervical cancer is a major global public health concern and ranks as the fourth most common cancer among women worldwide. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), approximately 604,000 new cases and 342,000 deaths occur each year due to cervical cancer, with the majority of cases reported in low- and middle-income countries. Despite being preventable through early detection and vaccination, cervical cancer continues to affect a large number of women due to lack of awareness, poor screening practices, and limited healthcare access.

Cervical cancer develops in the cervix due to abnormal cell growth, most commonly caused by persistent infection with high-risk types of Human Papillomavirus (HPV), especially HPV-16 and HPV-18 (Bosch et al., 2002). HPV is a sexually transmitted infection, and although many infections resolve naturally, persistent infection can lead to cancer if not treated early. Other risk factors include early marriage, multiple sexual partners, smoking, and weakened immune systems.

In developing countries such as Pakistan, cervical cancer is a growing health issue. Limited awareness, cultural barriers, and absence of national screening programs contribute to late diagnosis and high mortality rates (Siddiqua et al., 2023). Therefore, assessing awareness among healthcare students is important, as they will play a key role in prevention and education in the future.

1.2 Background of the Study:

The background provides general information about the topic and gradually narrows down to the specific problem. Cervical cancer is one of the most preventable cancers, yet it remains highly prevalent in developing countries. Globally, most cervical cancer cases are linked to HPV infection, which can be prevented through vaccination and screening (WHO, 2020).

However, in countries like Pakistan, lack of awareness and poor healthcare

1.3 THE GLOBAL SCENARIO

Cervical cancer remains a major global public health issue, affecting women worldwide, especially in low- and middle-income countries. In 2020 alone, researchers recorded about 604,000 new cases and 342,000 deaths. Early detection and HPV vaccination have made the disease largely preventable, prompting global initiatives like the WHO's "90-70-90" strategy. This plan targets vaccinating 90% of girls by age 15, screening 70% of women aged 35-45, and treating 90% of those diagnosed with cervical disease by 2030. Achieving these goals requires a thorough understanding of the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to HPV and its immunization across different populations. (Rahman et al 2025)

1.4 IMPECT OF HPV_s

High-risk HPV genotypes, especially HPV-16 and HPV-18, are responsible. Bivalent, quadrivalent, and nonvalent prophylactic HPV vaccines have shown strong effectiveness in preventing infections caused by these oncogenic strains. Prior infection with HPV reduces the vaccines' ability to lower cervical cancer incidence, yet the immunizations still demonstrate a remarkable capacity to cut cancer rates dramatically. In Bangladesh, HPV vaccination coverage remains low, making comprehensive understanding of the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to HPV and its vaccination crucial for designing interventions that boost vaccine acceptance and coverage. (Rahman at al 2025)

1.5 KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDES AND PRACTICE TOWARDS HPV

This systematic review protocol aims to update knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding human papillomavirus (HPV) and its vaccine to inform evidence-based policymaking in public health interventions. The study will synthesize existing KAP data and examine how variables such as country income, geography, age, and gender influence vaccination acceptance. The analysis will enable tailored solutions for specific barriers and facilitators across diverse demographic and socioeconomic contexts, thereby improving HPV vaccination programs. (Rahman at al 2025)

1.6 IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The significance of this study lies in understanding the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of BSN students, who are future healthcare. Assessing their KAP helps identify educational gaps and misconceptions, enabling the design of targeted programs to improve advocacy for HPV vaccination and cervical cancer screening among them, ultimately strengthening preventive healthcare initiatives. The strategies are synchronized with national health objectives and global programs aimed at lowering cervical cancer incidence and mortality. A Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) assessment of BSN students can uncover knowledge deficiencies and misconceptions that hinder effective

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cervical cancer prevention. Conducting such studies enables the creation of tailored training programs that prepare future healthcare with the knowledge and skills required to advocate for HPV vaccination and screening. This approach is essential for developing a competent healthcare workforce capable of addressing cervical cancer efficiently and supporting the attainment of global and national health targets. (Rahman et.,al 2025)

1.7 Problem Statement:

Despite the availability of preventive measures such as HPV vaccination and cervical screening, the incidence and mortality rates of cervical cancer remain high in developing countries. In Pakistan, there is limited awareness and poor screening practices among women and healthcare students. There is a need to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of BSN students regarding cervical cancer to identify gaps and improve educational strategies.

1.8 Significance of the Study:

This study is significant because it focuses on BSN students, who are future healthcare professionals. Their knowledge and practices directly influence patient education and community health. By identifying gaps in knowledge and attitudes, this study will help in designing targeted educational programs to improve cervical cancer prevention. It will also contribute to national and global efforts to reduce cervical cancer burden.

1.9 Aim of the Study

. This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to cervical cancer among BSN students at Liaquat College of Nursing, Jamshoro. By identifying gaps in awareness and practice, this research will contribute to the development of effective educational strategies and interventions to improve cervical cancer prevention. Ultimately, enhancing the knowledge and practices of future

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healthcare professionals will support national and global efforts to reduce the burden of cervical cancer.

Objectives of the Study:

To assess the level of knowledge about cervical cancer

To evaluate attitudes toward cervical cancer screening

To identify preventive practices among students

To analyze beliefs influencing screening behavior

Research Questions:

What is the level of knowledge about cervical cancer among BSN students?

What are the attitudes of students toward screening and prevention?

What practices do students follow regarding cervical cancer prevention?

Hypotheses**Null Hypothesis (H_0):**

There is no significant difference in knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding cervical cancer among BSN students.

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1):

There is a significant difference in knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding cervical cancer among BSN students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cervical cancer remains a significant public health concern globally, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) where it is the second most common cancer among women. In Ethiopia, cervical cancer is the second most common cancer and the second most deadly cancer among women.

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The main cause of cervical cancer is the Human Papillomavirus (HPV), which is transmitted through sexual intercourse. The Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices (KAP) towards cervical cancer screening are crucial for prevention and early detection. Studies have shown varying levels of KAP among different populations. For instance, a study in Nigeria found that knowledge and attitude towards cervical cancer screening were low among female university students. Similarly, a study in South Africa reported low uptake of cervical cancer screening among female university students. The study by Getaneh et al. (2021) aimed to assess the KAP of undergraduate female students towards cervical cancer screening at the University of Gondar, Northwest Ethiopia. The findings revealed that more than half of the respondents (59.3%) had good knowledge, whereas nearly 67.7% had a favorable attitude towards cervical cancer. However, less than 1% of the respondents had been screened for cervical cancer (Getaneh et al., 2021).

A cross-sectional study by Rahman et al. (2025) assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) regarding cervical cancer prevention among medical students in Bangladesh. The study found that most participants had moderate knowledge (78.2%) and positive attitudes (73.6%) toward cervical cancer prevention. However, practical engagement with preventive measures was notably low, with only 11.23% having received the HPV vaccine. The findings indicate gaps in preventive practices among medical students, despite their awareness of risk factors, symptoms, and prevention methods. Female students had significantly higher knowledge and attitude scores compared to males. This suggests a need for strengthening educational initiatives, integrating relevant content into curricula, and improving access to vaccination and screening. Responses are measured on a 5-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree). Scoring treats “Strongly Agree”/ “Agree” as correct for factual statements and uses reverse coding for negatively worded items. Knowledge scores range from 20 to 100 and are classified as good (80-100%), moderate (60-79%), or poor (<60%). (Rahman et al 2025)

The study examined cervical cancer (CC) awareness among female students in higher education institutions (HEI) in Cabo Verde. Key findings indicate that 86.2% of participants had little

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knowledge about CC and 67.3% held a negative attitude toward it. Almost all respondents (96.4%) had heard of CC, but 63.4% did not know its cause, and only 26.5% identified a virus as the cause, with 64.2% correctly linking it to HPV. Participants recognized multiple partners (63.3%) and family history (61.7%) as risk factors, while 17.7% associated smoking with CC. Awareness of symptoms was mixed: 61.7% knew CC has symptoms, but 37% were unaware. 72.9% identified abnormal blood loss as a symptom, and 49.1% linked urinary tract infection to CC. Regarding prevention, 32.3% recognized vaccination as a preventive measure, and 23.3% knew Pap smears are a screening method. 95% of respondents understood that late-stage CC can lead to death. In Cabo Verde, HPV prevalence is estimated at 4.3%, and 55.7% of CC cases are attributed to HPV16 and 18. The country introduced HPV vaccination in 2021 for 10-year-old girls but lacks structured screening programs and adequate healthcare infrastructure. (Rocha et al 2024)

The present study aims to assess KAP on CC screening among female higher-education students in Cabo Verde, addressing a data gap in the region. Assessing women's knowledge is crucial for designing effective intervention programs and health policies directed at CC prevention, especially since CC disproportionately affects younger women. The study highlights significant knowledge gaps and negative attitudes, emphasizing the need for educational interventions to improve CC prevention awareness and practices in Cabo Verde. (Rocha et al 2024)

Cross-sectional study investigated knowledge and attitude towards cervical cancer and its screening among women visiting the Gynecology Outpatient Department of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. This research is situated within the broader context of cervical cancer prevention in developing countries, particularly in South Asia, where incidence and mortality rates are high. Cervical Cancer Epidemiology: Cervical cancer is the second leading cause of mortality worldwide among non-communicable diseases (NCDs), with approximately 500,000 new cases annually and 270,000 deaths, 85% of which occur in developing countries, Pakistan faces a significant burden, with 20 women diagnosed daily Knowledge and Attitude towards Cervical Cancer: Studies show gaps in knowledge and attitude are critical barriers to screening uptake. In Pakistan, many women have limited

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awareness of cervical cancer and HPV. The current study found that 70.7% of respondents had low understanding of cervical cancer screening, and 29.3% had strong knowledge (Siddiqa et al., 2023). A descriptive Analysis study conducted in Pakistan assessed awareness and knowledge regarding cervical cancer screening among women attending gynecology outpatient departments. The study found that, 44.4% of patients had heard about cervical cancer, Awareness regarding Pap smear and HPV vaccination was present in around 20% of patients, Higher socio-economic status ($p=0.048$) and education ($p=0.03$) were linked to more awareness regarding cervical cancer. These findings suggest that targeted education and awareness programs may be effective in improving knowledge about cervical cancer screening among Pakistani women, particularly those from lower socio-economic backgrounds and with limited education. (Jafri et a.,2018)

Addressing the gaps in cervical cancer knowledge among BSN students requires multi-faceted approaches that combine health education, professional training, and policy interventions tailored to nursing curricula and clinical settings.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Design

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) related to cervical cancer among BSN students.

3.2 Study Setting

The study was conducted at Liaquat College of Nursing (LCON), which is affiliated with Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences.

3.3 Study Population

The study population consisted of all BSN 3rd-year and 4th-year students enrolled at LCON during the data collection period.

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Total population (N) = 100 students

3.4 Sample Size

The sample size was determined using the Rao soft sample size calculator. With a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, the calculated sample size was 80 participants.

Final sample size (n) = 80 students

3.5 Sampling Technique

A simple random sampling technique was used to select participants from 3rd and 4th year BSN students to ensure equal representation and minimize selection bias.

3.6 Inclusion Criteria

BSN 3rd and 4th year students

Students willing to participate

Students present during data collection

3.7 Exclusion Criteria

1st and 2nd year BSN students

Students absent during data collection

Students who refused to give consent

3.8 Data Collection Tool

Data were collected using a structured, self-administered questionnaire divided into four sections:

Section A: Demographic data (gender, name, religion, age, year of study, marital status,)

Section B: Attitude towards cervical cancer BSN students.

Section C: Attitude-related questions (beliefs and perceptions regarding screening and vaccination

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Section D: Practice-related questions

The questionnaire consisted of close-ended questions (multiple choice and Likert scale).

3.9 Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining permission from the principal of LCON, participants were informed about the purpose of the study. Written informed consent was obtained before distributing the questionnaires. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured. Data were collected over a period of 3 months from December to February.

3.10 Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using manually with excel Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to summarize the data. Chi-square test was applied to determine the association between variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3.11 Ethical Considerations

Informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained.

Participants had the right to withdraw at any time without penalty

Participants were given free hand to participate & decide whether they wanted to remain or quit from study.

Participants were given the right to opt to mention their name or not.

Participants were assured that research would not affect participants.

Participants were assured that record of research will be used for research purpose

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RESULTS

SECTION A. Demographic Information frequency and percentage(n=80)

AGE GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
20-22 years	33	44.25%
23-24 years	30	37.5%
25-26 years	9	9%
Above-26 years	7	9%

The questionnaire was distributed to 80 BSN students at the LCON. the distribution of respondents according to their age group. The majority of the respondents belong to the 20–22 years age group with 33 students (44.25%), followed by those aged 23–24 years with 30 students (37.5%). Meanwhile, 9 students (8.75%) fall within the 25–26 years age group, and 7 students (8.75%) are above 26 years old.

GENDER		
Female	80	100%
Male	0	0%

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The results indicate that all 80 respondents (100%) were female, while male respondents were not included in the sample.

Religion		
Islam	56	70%
Hindu	14	17%

The majority of respondents are Muslim (56 or about 70%), while Hindu respondents account for 14 (about 17%). This indicates that most participants in the study area belong to Islam, with a smaller proportion following Hinduism.

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Marital status		
Single	49	61.25%
Married	9	11.25%
Relation	8	10%
Divorce	3	3.75%

The majority are single (57 respondents, 71%), followed by married (10 respondents, 13%) and those in a relationship (10 respondents, 12%). Only 3 respondents (4%) are divorced, representing the smallest group. Overall, most respondents are single

Department		
BSN	80	99%

The data indicates that in the BSN department, out of 80 respondents, 99% belong to category 1, while only 1% is not include.

Study of Year		
3rd Year	32	40%
4 th Year	48	60%

The majority of respondents are 4th year students (60%), while 3rd year students represent 40% of the sample.

Section B: Attitude towards cervical cancer BSN student. (n=80)

QUESTION	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Whenever you notice infection, what do you do?	Looking for answer in natural medicine	12	15%
	Wait for the infection resolve spontaneously	15	18.75%
	Refer to a health care professional	32	40%
	Go to the pharmacy	21	26.25%

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Attends family planning consultation at the health center/gynecology?	Yes	48	60%
	No	31	38%

If yes, what is the reason?	Routine consultation /surveillance	36	45%
	Consultation for illness	12	15%

If no, what is the reason?	For not feeling the need	14	17.5%
	For not feeling the comfortable	12	15%
	Because the doctor is a man	5	6.25%

Beliefs about cervical cancer among BSN students. (n=80)

The chart presents the beliefs about cervical cancer among BSN students based on several perception-related statements. The responses are displayed as percentages across multiple categories of agreement, illustrating students' attitudes, fears, and perceptions regarding cervical cancer and cytology testing

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The questionnaire was distributed 80 students of BSN LCON FEMALE JAMSHORO 79 students responded were collected, with the regarding perceived susceptibility, 31% of respondents believed that it is likely they could develop cervical cancer, while 31.25% thought the probability of developing cervical cancer was moderate. Additionally, 32% felt that throughout their life they could potentially develop cervical cancer, and 34% believed they might be more likely to get cervical cancer compared to others.

Concerning emotional responses, a considerable proportion of students expressed fear and worry. Approximately 38% of respondents reported being worried that they might develop cervical cancer, while 45% stated that thinking about cervical cancer scares them. Furthermore, 53% indicated that they are afraid to think about cervical cancer, demonstrating a high level of anxiety related to the disease.

With regard to perceived seriousness, 46% of the participants believed that having cervical cancer would affect their whole life, and 36% thought that if they developed cervical cancer, they would not be able to live normally. These responses suggest that many students perceive cervical cancer as a serious and life-altering condition.

In relation to screening beliefs, 49% of respondents agreed that cytology testing can help detect uterine lesions earlier, indicating awareness of the importance of early detection. However, several concerns regarding the screening procedure were also identified. About 38% believed that cytology might be painful, 33% considered the test embarrassing, and 34% reported fear of undergoing a cytology test. Additionally, 30% believed that if cytology shows a lesion in the uterus, it would cause significant concern.

SECTION. D Belief about cervical cancer among BSN students. (n=80)

Question	Strongly disagree (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Undecided (%)	Strongly agree (%)
Do you think it is likely that you could get cervical cancer?	31%	9%	30.00%	23.75%	0%
Do you think that the probability of developing cervical cancer in the next few years is high?	21.25%	31.25%	23.75%	13.75%	8.75%
Dou you feel that throughout your life you could have cervical cancer?	31.25%	6.25%	33.72%	20.00%	2.50%
Do you think you are more likely to get cervical cancer than most women?	32%	21%	28%	14%	4%
Is the development of cervical cancer something you may be experiencing right now?	34%	14%	36%	8%	9%
Are you worried that you might develop cervical cancer in the near future?	25%	20%	29%	20%	5%
Does thinking about cervical cancer scare you?	8%	38%	19%	12%	19%
When you think about cervical cancer, does your heartbeat faster?	10%	45%	14%	19%	13%

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Are you afraid to think about cervical cancer?	10%	53%	10%	6%	15%
Do you think that if you had cervical cancer the problems you would have last a long time?	26%	29%	20%	18%	6%
Do you think if you had cervical cancer your whole life would change?	18%	46%	13%	11%	10%
If I develop cervical cancer, wouldn't I live more than 5 years?	19%	19%	24%	36%	0%
Does the cytology help detect uterine lesions earlier?	9%	49%	16%	16%	6%
If the cytology shows a lesion in the uterus, won't the cancer treatment be so bad?	16%	33%	24%	25%	1%
Are you afraid of having a cytology test because you won't understand how it is done?	10%	34%	26%	23%	6%
Would a cytology test be embarrassing?	15%	25%	33%	24%	3%
Would a cytology be painful?	6%	38%	10%	30%	15%
Do you have other problem more important than thinking about doing a cytology?	21%	20%	35%	19%	4%

Overall, the data show that results demonstrate that although many BSN students recognize the seriousness of cervical cancer and the importance of cytology screening for early detection, a substantial proportion still experience fear, anxiety, and misconceptions related to the disease and the screening procedure.

SECTION. E KNOWLEDGE REGARDING CERVICAL CANCER AMONG BSN STUDENT

Questions	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Cervical cancer is one of the most common cancers among women	(52.5)	(37.5)	(0)	(10)	(0)
Did you learn about cervical cancer from teacher	(26.5)	(15)	(8.75)	(27.5)	(22.5)
Cervical cancer is preventable	(47.5)	(16.25)	(5)	(17.5)	(11.25)
Smoking cigarettes causes cervical cancer	(17.5)	(20)	(2.5)	(13.75)	(12.5)
Having a positive family history is a risk factor	(22.5)	16.25	21.25	22.25	17.5
Multiple pregnancies (≥ 4 vaginal births) are linked with increased risk of cervical cancer	27.5	17.5	23.75	26.25	5
Cervical cancer is a sexually transmitted infection					
Obesity increases the risk of cervical cancer	29 (36.25)	15 (18.75)	11 (13.75)	19 (23.75)	6 (7.5%)
Cervical cancer is most commonly associated with persistent HPV	18 (22.5)	12 (15)	9 (11.25)	25 (31.25)	15 (18.75)

infection					
Irregular vaginal bleeding is a symptom of cervical cancer	51 (63.75)	22 (27.5)	0 (0)	4 (5)	3 (3.75)
Foul-smelling vaginal discharge, vaginal irregular bleeding, are the symptom	49(61.25)	14 (17.5)	2 (2.5)	7 (8.75)	8 (10)
Cancer of the cervix can be cured in earliest stage	21 (26.25)	23 (28.25)	13 (16.25)	17 (21.25)	6 (7.5)

CHAPTER 5:

5.1 Discussion

The present study was conducted to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) related to cervical cancer among BSN students at Liaquat College of Nursing, Jamshoro. The findings revealed that students had moderate knowledge, generally positive attitudes, but poor preventive practices, particularly regarding screening and vaccination.

Knowledge

The results of this study indicate that most students were aware that cervical cancer is a common disease and recognized key symptoms such as abnormal vaginal bleeding and foul-smelling discharge. However, gaps were identified in understanding risk factors and the role of Human Papillomavirus (HPV) in the development of cervical cancer.

These findings are consistent with the study by Rahman et al. (2025), which reported that medical students had moderate knowledge (78.2%) about cervical cancer but lacked comprehensive understanding of preventive measures. Similarly, Getaneh et al. (2021) found that although more than half of the participants had good knowledge, there were still deficiencies in specific areas.

Attitude

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The study showed that students generally had a positive attitude toward cervical cancer prevention. A majority preferred consulting healthcare professionals when facing health issues, and many acknowledged the importance of screening for early detection.

However, emotional barriers such as fear, embarrassment, and anxiety were also identified. Many respondents expressed concern about undergoing screening procedures, perceiving them as painful or uncomfortable. These findings are in line with Rocha et al. (2024), where students reported fear and negative perceptions regarding cervical cancer screening.

Practices

Despite having moderate knowledge and positive attitudes, the actual practices of students were found to be inadequate. A significant proportion of students had not undergone cervical cancer screening and did not regularly utilize healthcare services.

This gap between knowledge and practice is supported by multiple studies. Getaneh et al. (2021) reported that less than 1% of participants had undergone screening, despite having good knowledge. Similarly, Siddiqa et al. (2023) highlighted that screening practices among Pakistani women remain very low due to lack of awareness and cultural barriers.

Comparison with Other Studies

The findings of this study are consistent with national and international literature, which shows that awareness alone does not necessarily lead to behavioral change. Factors such as cultural beliefs, lack of accessibility, fear, and social stigma significantly influence preventive practices.

In Pakistan, Jafri et al. (2018) also reported low awareness and poor screening uptake among women. These similarities indicate that the issue is widespread and requires targeted interventions at both educational and policy levels.

5.2 Conclusion

The study concludes that BSN students at Liaquat College of Nursing have moderate knowledge and positive attitudes toward cervical cancer; however, their preventive practices are inadequate.

Although most students are aware of cervical cancer and its seriousness, many lack detailed knowledge about risk factors and prevention methods such as HPV vaccination and screening. Emotional barriers, including fear and embarrassment, further contribute to poor screening practices.

This gap between knowledge and practice highlights the need for structured educational programs and awareness campaigns. As future healthcare professionals, nursing students must be equipped with accurate knowledge and practical skills to promote cervical cancer prevention effectively.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

Educational Interventions

Integrate cervical cancer education into the nursing curriculum

Conduct regular awareness sessions and workshops

Provide training on HPV vaccination and screening procedures

Awareness Programs

Organize health campaigns in colleges and communities

Use media platforms to spread awareness about cervical cancer prevention

Address myths, misconceptions, and cultural barriers

Healthcare Services

Improve accessibility to cervical cancer screening services

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Ensure availability of female healthcare providers to reduce discomfort

Promote regular health check-ups among students

Policy Recommendations

Implement national screening programs

Introduce HPV vaccination programs at institutional levels

Strengthen public health policies for cancer prevention

Further Research

Conduct studies on larger populations

Explore barriers to screening in depth

Evaluate the effectiveness of educational interventions

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